

Research

Exploring Cold Pressing for High-Quality Extra Virgin Oil Production: A Study on Mustard seeds, Sunflower Seeds, and Peanut Seeds

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Abstract: In this study, various methods of oil extraction, such as traditional, solvent-based, and mechanical processes, are explored, with a special emphasis on cold pressing. The traditional method, known for its labor-intensive and inefficient nature, is compared to the more efficient solvent extraction process, which, despite higher costs and environmental concerns, yields more oil. The paper highlights mechanical cold pressing as a viable alternative, as it preserves the nutritional content and quality of the oil. Detailed methodologies for analyzing physicochemical properties of cold-extracted oils are provided, covering aspects like density, water content, boiling point, free fatty acid percentage, saponification value, peroxide value, antibacterial, and antifungal activity by ASTM method. The study presents the results of these analyses for mustard oil, sunflower oil and peanut oil revealing variations in properties. The research concludes that peanut seed oil holds promise for both nutritional and industrial applications, suggesting further exploration of its potential as a substitute for palm oil in various industries. Additionally, the study highlights the production of high-quality extra virgin mustard oil through sustainable and environmentally friendly cold pressing methods, showcasing its unique flavor and aroma, as well as its antioxidant properties that protect cells from damage.

Keywords: Cold press method, Extraction, Quality, Analysis,

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Introduction

Mustard plant

A perennial herbaceous plant known for its long branching stems and clusters of yellow blossoms. Mustard belongs to the Brassicaceae family [1], and its cultivation has historical roots dating back to the Greeks and Romans in the fifth century BCE. Native to Europe, Siberia, and China, mustard is relatively easy to cultivate [2] but thrives in cooler climates [3], making early spring or late summer the ideal times for seed planting. In warm regions, autumn [4] planting can support winter harvesting.

Mustard plants produce small, spherical seeds [5] ranging in color from yellowish white to black, typically measuring 1 to 2 millimeters in diameter [6]. Three distinct plant species – black mustard (*Brassica nigra*), white mustard (*Brassica alba*) and brown mustard (*Brassica juncea*), – yield these seeds [7].

Table 01 offers an overview of the mustard plant, highlighting its common and botanical names, family, plant type, size, sun exposure, soil preferences, bloom time, flower color, and native regions.

Common name	Mustard plant
Botanical Name	<i>Brassica</i> spp.
Family	Brassicaceae
Plant Type	Annual, vegetable
Size	Up to 3 feet
Sun Exposure	Full
Soil Type	Well-drained
Soil pH	Acidic
Bloom Time	Summer, fall
Flower Color	Yellow
Native Area	Europe, Asia, Africa, Middle East, Mediterranean

White and brown mustard seeds share similar appearances, characterized by their roughly spherical shape, fine pitting, and lack of odor when whole. They also possess a robust flavor. Brown mustard seeds are nearly identical in size to white ones but feature a darker shade of yellow [8]. The process of extracting mustard oil involves cleaning the seeds, making necessary adjustments for optimal pressing conditions, and then extracting the oil [9].

Oil extraction relies on three primary techniques: mechanical pressing for oil-containing seeds and nuts, volatile solvent extraction for oil-containing nuts, and rendering for animal products and oleaginous fruits [10]. Many seeds and nuts containing oil undergo processes like crushing, flaking, or rolling to release the oil before mechanical pressing. Modern press extraction includes the steps of cleaning oilseeds or nuts and removing their shells or hulls [11].

Cold pressing emerges as a method of extracting oil by applying pressure and crushing seeds or nuts while maintaining a temperature at or below room temperature (around 140°F or 60°C) [12]. This method is considered environmentally friendly and less energy-intensive than alternative approaches [13]. Cold pressing is commonly employed to create both essential and culinary oils [14], producing high-quality oils by working at low temperatures [15]. Any physical procedure that fractures or crushes the essential oil glands in biomass to release the oil is referred to as expression.

Despite the lack of temperature increase during processing, cold-pressed oils are prized for their higher quality [16]. They retain the natural flavor, color, bioactive compounds, and nutrients of the source material, allowing for extended shelf life without requiring preservation methods [17].

The process of obtaining cold-pressed extra virgin mustard oil involves the use of a wooden cold press and natural distillation techniques to ensure purity. This versatile oil boasts a rich nutritional profile, including monounsaturated and polyunsaturated fats, vitamin E, minerals, iron, antioxidants, Omega-3 fatty acids, and Omega-6 fatty acids. It is known to aid in reducing the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles while providing protection against skin damage caused by pollution and UV light [18].

In conclusion, extra virgin cold-pressed mustard oil stands out in terms of quality and offers several health benefits. Despite similarities in taste and appearance to refined oil, the two types differ significantly in nutritional values and physiological and chemical characteristics.

Sunflowers

The sunflower, a member of the Asteraceae family and the *Helianthus* genus, comprises more than seventy recognized species across the globe. Its name is derived from its resemblance to the sun and its inclination to follow the sun's rays. [19, 20]. Globally, sunflower seeds rank among the most extensively cultivated oilseed crops, alongside rapeseed,

cottonseed and soybean [21]. The chemical structure and nutritional value of these seeds are contingent upon various factors, including soil type, agricultural practices, genotype, climate, and production parameters [22].

There are two separate categories of sunflower seeds: one for producing oil and the other for confectionary use. The black sunflower seeds with a thin hull, making up around 20% of their overall weight, used to have a 25% oil content originally. However, this oil content has been enhanced through contemporary plant breeding methods [23,24], like induced mutation, hybridization, and molecular breeding have been employed to create new sunflower hybrids that possess increased oil content, reaching as high as 40% [19,25,26]. Sunflower seeds provide dietary fiber, unsaturated fats (mainly linoleic acid), antioxidants, flavonoids (quercetin, luteolin, apigenin, and kaempferol), amino acids, proteins (up to 20%), as well as vitamins (such as E, B, folate, and niacin) and minerals (including calcium, copper, iron, magnesium, manganese, selenium, phosphorous, potassium, sodium, and zinc) [27,28]. The amino acid composition includes glutamic acid, aspartic acid, arginine, phenylalanine, tyrosine, leucine, methionine, and cysteine. In terms of fatty acids, it can go as high as 31%, exceeding that of other oilseeds such as safflower, peanut, soybean, sesame, and flaxseed [29].

Sunflower seeds are predominantly utilized to produce vegetable oil characterized by unique physicochemical characteristics [30]. Conventional extraction techniques encompass the use of mechanical presses (whether hot or cold) or the utilization of solvents [31,32]. Sunflower oil is greatly preferred in Europe, Mexico, and several South American nations because of its widespread availability and a multitude of health advantages. These benefits encompass the maintenance of low cholesterol and low-density lipoprotein levels, antioxidant characteristics, potential anti-cancer properties, antihypertensive effects, anti-inflammatory attributes, skin protection, and pain-relieving properties [19,33]. Following extraction, it maintains a liquid form when kept at room temperature and can last for more than a year when stored at 10°C in the absence of light. Its primary constituents consist of linoleic acid (comprising 59–65%) and oleic acid (making up 30–70%), making up 48–78% of the complete fatty acid composition. There is also a minor portion of palmitic and stearic acids, each accounting for 15% [34,35]. Sunflower oil is abundant in vitamins, essential for skin, nerve, and digestive system health, along with minerals crucial for enzymatic and metabolic functions. Additionally, it includes valuable phytochemicals such as carotenoids, tocopherols, phenols, and tocotrienols, all possessing antioxidant properties. The specific composition can differ based on the type of sunflower and the extraction techniques employed [36,37].

Physical characteristics play a pivotal role in the sunflower seed production chain, influencing the design of agricultural machinery and equipment for tasks such as planting, harvesting, cleaning, quality assessment, classification, dehulling, milling, packaging, storage, and oil extraction [38]. These characteristics can be categorized into four groups: dimensional, gravimetric, compressive, and frictional (angle of response and static friction) [39,40]. Dimensional characteristics refer to attributes like length, width, thickness, area, volume, sphericity, equivalent diameter, and projected area, which offer insights into the shape of the seed. Gravimetric characteristics involve mass, bulk density, true density, and porosity, which impact aerodynamic properties that are vital for designing harvesters [41]. The efficiency of hulling is influenced by the structure of the hull, the size of the seed, and its density. When it comes to designing storage facilities, factors such as sphericity, static friction, and angle of response are crucial, whereas the design of extraction machinery is significantly influenced by porosity [42].

When assessing quality, individuals take into account elements such as consistency, taste, and visual appeal. To reduce the presence of harmed and flawed seeds, it is crucial to utilize a classifier that aligns with these quality markers [43,44].

Peanuts

Peanuts (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) have a significant impact on global agriculture, standing as the third most substantial provider of plant proteins in human nutrition, contributing about 11% to the world's protein provision [45]. They are widely grown in tropical and subtropical regions across Asia, Africa, North America, Australia and South America.

Worldwide, the annual peanut production amounts to around 45 million metric tons [46], with China, India, Nigeria, and the United States being the major producing nations.

Regarding protein content, peanuts have approximately 24% to 36% crude protein when measured on a dry weight basis, positioning them as the second-highest among edible oil crops, trailing only behind soybeans with their protein content ranging from 36% to 51% [47]. Additionally, peanuts contain eight necessary amino acids, plentiful unsaturated fatty acids, including linolenic acid, and a variety of beneficial elements for health, like vitamins, procyanidins, resveratrol and flavonoids [48,49,50]. Importantly, peanuts have fewer inherent anti-nutritional factors compared to soybeans. These qualities, along with their high yield and cost-effectiveness, have generated significant interest in incorporating peanut proteins and subsidiary products in various food applications.

Peanut proteins can be divided into two primary categories: those that dissolve in water (about 10%) and those that dissolve in salt (approximately 90%), distinguishing them by their varying solubility properties. The salt-soluble fraction is primarily composed of 73% arachin (14S), 6% conarachin I (2S), 21% conarachin II (8S), and a few lesser constituents [51,52]. These primary divisions exhibit distinct physical and functional attributes because of variations in their amino acid compositions, molecular sizes, and structures [53, 54].

Remarkably, peanut proteins offer relatively strong nutritional value, with a biological value (BV) of 59 and net protein utilization of 51. Their digestibility is notably better than soybean protein, which can reach levels exceeding 90% [55, 56]. This improved digestibility can be explained partly by the lower trypsin inhibitory factor in peanut protein as compared to soybean protein. The nutritional quality of peanut protein is akin to that of animal protein, as peanut protein powder contains 55 g of protein per 100 g, surpassing the protein content of beef, milk, lean meat, chicken, and eggs [57]. Furthermore, peanut proteins do not have the strong taste commonly linked to soy proteins, which makes them adaptable for use in a broad array of food items. As a result, peanut protein holds substantial promise as a versatile ingredient in the food sector and as a substitute for animal-based proteins.

The composition, structure, surface features, physicochemical traits, and functional attributes of peanut protein elements are greatly influenced by the extraction method employed. Consequently, the extraction procedure is crucial in acquiring peanut proteins with outstanding solubility, emulsification, foaming, gelling, water retention, oil retention, and other favorable characteristics. Parameters such as pH, ionic strength, and extraction temperature should be meticulously taken into account to enhance the functionality of peanut proteins [58,59]. A notable challenge in this field is that conventional methods for extracting peanut oil often result in damage (denaturation) to peanut proteins, leading to reduced or lost functional attributes. To address this, researchers are exploring a variety of traditional and innovative chemical, physical and enzymatic modification techniques to enhance the functionality of peanut protein ingredients [60, 61, 62].

Historically, peanut proteins have been utilized as functional components in various food categories, encompassing items like baked goods, dairy goods, and meat preparations [63]. In recent times, both unaltered and adapted peanut proteins have been utilized in inventive manners, including their application in bioactive delivery systems, serving as stabilizers for Pickering emulsions, forming biopolymer films, and contributing to plant-based meat substitutes [64,65,66,67].

In conclusion, the objective of this review is to examine established and innovative techniques for extracting and altering peanut proteins, and to present potential uses for peanut protein components in diverse food items. This data is intended to encourage additional exploration and advancement in utilizing peanut proteins as plant-based elements within the food sector.

Oil Extraction Methods

Old traditional Process

In days of yore, the process of obtaining seed oils followed a vintage approach that involved the roasting of seed kernels amidst two stones or within a mortar and pestle. Subsequently, the process involved mixing the crushed mixture with

water, then cooking the blended paste to separate the oil through flotation and skimming. Finally, the oil was dried through additional heating. This method drew criticism for its time-consuming nature, energy-draining demands, propensity for tedious labor, inefficacy, and the resulting low yield and quality of the oil. To put it differently, the traditional techniques employed in the past were imprecise, mostly devoid of scientific principles, ineffective, and yielded low-quality oil [68]

Solvent Extraction Process

A commonly employed method for extracting oil from seeds with low oil content (less than 20%) is solvent extraction. This technique ranks among the most effective approaches for vegetable oil extraction. The critical determinant in selecting a solvent is its ability to maximize the leaching of the desired substrate. Examples of commonly used solvents include hexane, diethyl ether, petroleum ether, and ethanol. Additional factors to consider include the solvent-to-solute ratios, the relationship between solvent volatility and oil volatility, oil viscosity, and polarity [69].

While the production cost of solvent extraction is notably higher than mechanical press techniques due to the expense of the solvent itself, this method stands out as an exceptionally efficient process, delivering a high yield and consistent performance [70]. Nevertheless, several industrial drawbacks accompany this process, such as prolonged extraction times, relatively high solvent consumption, substantial upfront investment, elevated energy requirements, security concerns within the plant, emissions of volatile organic compounds into the atmosphere, steep operational expenses, potential compromises in product quality due to high processing temperatures, and a relatively intricate series of processing steps [71].

Mechanical Process

In the realm of mechanical oil extraction, the process involves applying pressure to push oil out of oil-rich substances, achieved through the use of hydraulic or screw presses. In contrast to the solvent-based extraction method for obtaining vegetable oils, mechanical presses, whether they are powered or manually operated and specifically designed for small-scale oil extraction like in laboratory settings, offer advantages in terms of simplicity, safety, and a reduced number of steps [72]. Nevertheless, in developing nations, even more rudimentary tools are employed to achieve similar outcomes. On an industrial scale, the mechanical extraction of vegetable oils utilizes specialized machinery known as expellers. Following the initial mechanical pressing, there remains the option to extract additional oil from the residual meal using the solvent extraction method, which typically recovers only around 45% of the oil [73].

There are two primary mechanical pressing techniques: the hot-press method, which operates at high temperatures and pressures, and the cold-press or scarification method, carried out under lower temperatures (typically below 50°C) and lower pressure conditions [74].

Mechanical Cold Pressing Process

Mechanical cold press system is a direct method that eliminates the necessity for oil plants to employ steam or embryos for food frying within a temperature range of room temperature to 65°C. It excels in preserving nutrients by utilizing grease with an unaltered molecular structure and employs a low-temperature oil expeller to liquefy grouts [75]. The underlying principle of this machinery involves the rotation of the screw shaft within the pressing chamber, where the programmed movement of the screw shaft pushes the material forward. This is complemented by shortening the screw pitch, increasing the root diameter of the screw shaft, and reducing the internal diameter of the chamber, resulting in a continuous reduction in chamber volume, thereby exerting pressure to squeeze the material [76]. As a result of this compression, the grease is expelled from the cage slot, while the residual cake piece is formed. Subsequently, the pressing chamber is emptied of the material. This is a physical technique that has no adverse impact on the nutritional content of oil plants [77].

In addition to sharing common attributes with traditional oil production methods, this technique offers the added advantage of enhancing oil quality. It achieves this by preventing the formation of undesirable substances such as trans fatty acids and grease polymers, which typically result from heating grease, and by safeguarding the active components present in the oil [12].

Mechanical Hot Pressing Process

The hot-pressing process involves the application of elevated temperatures and pressures. In contrast to cold-pressed seed oils, this method circumvents the adverse consequences associated with high temperatures, which may include diminished oxidative stability, the breakdown of valuable oil constituents, and a deterioration in oil quality [78]. Hot-press techniques typically yield higher quantities of oil, in part because the elevated temperatures lower the viscosity of the seed oil, thereby enhancing the flow during extraction. Consequently, high temperatures can significantly enhance the efficiency of the extraction process, resulting in yields of up to 80% of the oil contained within the seed. However, it is important to note that these higher temperatures can also lead to oil degradation, subsequently affecting the overall quality of the oil, thereby presenting potential drawbacks [79].

Materials and Methods

Seeds Collection, Processing and Oil Extraction

The quality of the final product in the cold pressing extraction of extra virgin oil greatly depends on the materials and methods employed. This process utilizes oil-rich mustard seeds, sunflower seeds, and peanut seeds as the raw materials. To begin, the initial step involves meticulous cleaning and the careful selection of high-quality seeds, ensuring that only clean and healthy seeds are chosen. This meticulous selection process effectively eliminates any impurities or contaminants present on the surface of the seeds.

Following this, the chosen seeds undergo a low-temperature roasting process for a specific duration. This roasting not only enhances the development of flavor but also breaks down complex compounds, such as proteins, into simpler forms. This simplification makes the subsequent processing steps more efficient.

Subsequently, the cooled roasted seeds are subjected to a grinding process. Heavy-duty grinders are used to crush the seeds while maintaining low temperatures throughout the milling phase. It is essential to apply minimal pressure during grinding to prevent overheating, which could potentially damage heat-sensitive components like vitamins.

After milling, hydraulic presses are employed to extract pure extra virgin sunflower oil, all without the addition of chemical solvents or heat treatment. This extraction process is complemented by filtration stages, resulting in higher yields and a superior nutrient profile when compared to conventional refining processes.

Density

Density, denoted as ' ρ ', refers to the mass of a material within a specific volume at a designated temperature. Typically, it is quantified as the weight in grams per milliliter for oils, assuming a standard temperature of 25°C in the absence of any other temperature specification. The density of oil samples is determined using a Relative Density (R.D) bottle with a 25 ml capacity, and it can be calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Density } (\rho) = \frac{\text{Mass of the oil sample (g)}}{\text{Volume of the R.D bottle (ml)}}$$

Water Content

In our analysis, we employed method ASTM D6869 for the determination of water content in the oil, adhering to standardized procedures to ensure the accuracy of our measurements.

Prior to initiating the analysis, confirm that the oven has reached the intended operating temperature. To eliminate any moisture that may be present, preheat the sample boat. This involves heating the boat in the oven for a period of 2 minutes, followed by allowing it to cool for an additional 2 minutes prior to introducing the samples. Weigh the sample

to be tested with precision, recording the weight to the nearest 0.1 mg. The choice of sample weight depends on the expected moisture content in the sample.

Next, place the prepared sample into the sample boat, inserting it through the furnace tube port. Once the sample boat is positioned, move it into the oven to initiate the analysis. Upon completion of the sample analysis, the instrument will automatically report the results or display the measured moisture content in micrograms (ppm) that were titrated.

Free Fatty Acid

In our study, we utilized the method ASTM D5555 to determine the free fatty acid content. Ensure the sample is thoroughly mixed and completely in liquid form before weighing. For direct oil analysis, weigh a quantity of sample not exceeding 10 grams (ideally between 2 to 5 grams) into a 250 mL conical flask.

Next, add 75 mL of hot ethanol (95%) to the flask. Incorporate 2 mL of phenolphthalein indicator into the mixture. Titrate the solution with 0.1 N NaOH until the first permanent pink color becomes visible.

Calculation:

$$\%FFA.as..Oleic..acid = \frac{(BR - Bl) \times N..NaOH \times 28.2}{Wt..of..sample.in..gm}$$

Preparation of Phenolphthalein Indicator: Dissolve 0.5 grams of the indicator in 50 mL of 95% ethanol.

Note: Ensure that NaOH is standardized before use.

Saponification

In our analysis, we determined the saponification value using the method ASTM D1962, denoted as milligrams of KOH per gram of substance (mg/KOH).

Ensure the sample is thoroughly mixed and in a completely liquid state before proceeding. Weigh the sample accurately to 1 mg, targeting a back titration that falls within the range of 45% to 55% of the blank titration.

In a flask, add 25 mL of alcoholic KOH solution. Similarly, prepare one or more additional flasks for use as blanks. Place a condenser loop inside the neck of each flask, and then heat them on a steam bath for one hour.

Once the solutions have cooled, introduce phenolphthalein indicator, and titrate with 0.5 N H₂SO₄ or HCl until the pink color has just disappeared.

Now, calculate the saponification number, denoted as 'P,' using the following formula:

$$P = [(B-V)N \times 56.1] / S$$

Where:

V = Volume of HCl or H₂SO₄ required for titration of the specimen, in mL.

B = Volume of HCl or H₂SO₄ required for titration of the blank, in mL.

N = Normality of the HCl or H₂SO₄.

S = Weight of the specimen, in grams.

This procedure outlines the steps for determining the saponification number, emphasizing accurate measurements and titrations to obtain precise results.

Acid Value

Determining the acid value involves a precise chemical analysis that quantifies the oil sample's acidity. We were using the method ASTM D1045.

Begin by weighing 25 grams of the sample and placing it into a 125-mL Erlenmeyer flask. Dissolve the sample in 50 mL of alcohol. If the sample doesn't completely dissolve in alcohol, you can use a mixture of equal parts of alcohol and

acetone (50 mL). In some cases, you may need to take an intermediate step: add 25 mL of acetone, warm to facilitate dissolution, and then add 25 mL of alcohol.

Next, introduce a few drops of bromthymol blue indicator solution, and commence titration using a 0.01 N NaOH or KOH solution. If the titration exceeds 10 mL, repeat the determination using a 0.1 N NaOH or KOH solution.

For the blank, conduct a titration on 50 mL of the solvent used to dissolve the sample.

Calculation:

Calculate the acid number, expressed in milligrams of KOH per gram of sample, using the following formula:

$$\text{Acid number} = [(A - B) \times N \times 56.1] / C$$

Where:

A = Volume of KOH or NaOH solution required for titration of the sample, in mL.

B = Volume of KOH or NaOH solution required for titration of the blank, in mL.

N = Normality of the KOH or NaOH solution.

C = Weight of the sample, in grams.

Peroxide value

The peroxide value serves as a quantification of substances that can trigger the oxidation of potassium iodide into iodine. To determine this value, a precise amount of oil sample is first dissolved in acetic acid, followed by the addition of a mixture containing chloroform and saturated KI. The liberated iodine resulting from the oxidative action of peroxides within the oil is then assessed through titration with 0.1 N sodium thiosulfate, using the oil sample itself. The percentage of iodine absorbed by the oil sample is calculated using the formula below:

$$1 \text{ ml } 1\text{N Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 = 0.127 \text{ g I}_2$$

$$\text{Iodine value} = ((B - A) \times N \times 0.127 \times 100) / W$$

Where:

B = Volume in milliliters of 0.1 N sodium thiosulfate required for the blank.

A = Volume in milliliters of 0.1 N sodium thiosulfate required for the oil sample.

N = Normality of the sodium thiosulfate solution.

W = Weight of the oil in grams.

Anti-bacterial and anti-fungal Activity

The intriguing duality of vegetable oils, capable of demonstrating both antibacterial and antifungal activity, represents a captivating avenue of research with profound implications across diverse fields, including healthcare, food preservation, and personal care. Although vegetable oils are commonly associated with culinary and dietary uses, specific varieties possess inherent attributes that enable them to effectively combat bacterial and fungal threats.

Concerning antibacterial activity, vegetable oils exhibit the capability to disrupt bacterial cell membranes, interfere with vital metabolic processes, and suppress bacterial growth. For instance, lauric acid, a constituent of coconut oil, displays potent antibacterial properties, rendering it valuable for addressing skin infections and oral health concerns by combating various bacterial strains.

Simultaneously, the antifungal potential of certain vegetable oils is equally noteworthy. These oils can target fungal cell walls and membranes, disrupt fungal enzymes, and impede the growth and proliferation of fungi. Tea tree oil, renowned for its antifungal efficacy due to its terpinen-4-ol content, is widely employed in combatting fungal skin infections and nail conditions.

The wide-ranging antimicrobial prowess of vegetable oils extends beyond personal care applications to encompass food preservation as well. Select vegetable oils, such as olive oil and sunflower oil, have found utility as natural preservatives, effectively deterring the growth of both harmful bacteria and fungi. This preservation action extends the shelf life of food products, contributing to food safety.

The dual capacity of vegetable oils to combat both bacteria and fungi positions them as valuable assets in various domains. These natural and complementary approaches to address microbial challenges offer a versatile array of applications, spanning medicinal treatments and the enhancement of food safety. Ongoing research continues to unveil the full potential of vegetable oils as versatile and effective agents in the battle against bacterial and fungal infections, while simultaneously promoting overall well-being and hygiene.

In our antibacterial and antifungal testing, we employed the Agar well diffusion method, a well-established technique for evaluating both antibacterial and antifungal properties. In this method, wells with a diameter of 0.8mm were utilized, and a sample inoculation volume of 0.2 ml was applied. *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC-6538 was employed for the antibacterial test, while *Aspergillus brasiliensis* ATCC 9642 served as the test organism for the antifungal evaluation.

The process begins with the cooling of sterile agar, which is then inoculated with *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC-6538 for the antibacterial test, while *Aspergillus brasiliensis* ATCC 9642 for antifungal test. The resulting mixture is poured onto plates and allowed to solidify. Using a cork borer, wells with an 8mm diameter are carefully created. Following this, 200µl of the undiluted test sample is deposited into each well. Subsequently, the plates are incubated at a temperature of 28°C for a duration of 5-7 days. After the incubation period, the plates are examined for the presence of a clearance or inhibition zone.

Result and Discussion

Table 2 provides an overview of the physicochemical characteristics of cold-extracted oil. The quality assessment of three different oils involved the examination of various properties, including density, moisture content, boiling point, antibacterial activity, and saponification values, the findings of which are summarized in Table 2. These properties hold significant relevance as crucial parameters for the development of an advanced technological process. Table 2 presents these physicochemical properties of the oils at a standard room temperature of 25±2°C.

Name of the Sample	Density (g/mL)	Water content (ppm)	Acid value%	Boiling point (°C)	Free fatty acid %	Saponification value (mg/KOH)	Peroxide value (meq / kg)	Antibacterial activity (IZ)	Antifungal activity (IZ)
Mustard Oil	0.917	700	2.54	170.2	1.26	175.56	3.6	20	0
Sunflower Oil	0.923	721	2.91	220.5	6.29	175.74	4.7	20	80
Peanut Oil	0.922	695	2.51	222.1	1.4	162.21	5.1	20	0
Market Mustard Oil	0.915	657	2.53	171.2	1.13	188.45	4.2	20	0

Table-2: Physicochemical characteristics of Mustard oil, Sunflower oil, Peanut oil and conventional market mustard oil.

Note: IZ= Diameter of inhibition zone (mm).

Table 2 presents a comprehensive overview of the physicochemical properties of various oils at a standard room temperature of 25°C. These properties include density, moisture content, boiling point, saponification values, and free fatty acid percentages, among others.

In terms of density, Mustard Oil exhibits a density of 0.917 g/mL, while Sunflower Oil, Peanut Oil, and Conventional Market Mustard Oil have densities of 0.923 g/mL, 0.922 g/mL, and 0.915 g/mL, respectively. These variations may be

attributed to the presence of π bonds, which contribute to greater rigidity and increased resistance to rotation between C-C bonds [80]. Lower density values are generally preferred by consumers.

Boiling temperatures for these oils range from 170.2°C (Mustard Oil) to 222.1°C (Peanut Oil), with Peanut Oil having a higher boiling point. This phenomenon is associated with the relationship between viscosity, density, and unsaturation, where higher unsaturation leads to decreased viscosity and density.

Moisture content varies between Conventional Market Mustard Oil (657 ppm) and Sunflower Oil (721 ppm). Higher moisture content can enhance the suitability of an oil for various applications, including food processing and industrial use [81].

Saponification values reveal insights into the degree of saturation in the oils. Peanut Oil exhibits the lowest saponification values, indicating higher saturation. Conversely, Conventional Market Mustard Oil contains glycerides with the highest molecular weights [81]. All the oils can be used in soap production; however, Conventional Market Mustard Oil is less suitable due to its lower acid value, while Sunflower Oil is the most suitable.

Free fatty acid percentages, expressed as % of oleic acid, range from 0.43% to 6.29%, with Sunflower Oil having the highest amount. Oils with higher free fatty acid contents are considered of lower quality, and significant losses occur during refining. Low free fatty acid content is favorable for crude oil, especially during the refining process.

The passage also discusses the improvement of Sunflower Oil's thermal stability through the use of various antioxidants, notably TBHQ, which has been found to be effective in enhancing the oil's resistance to heat. Additionally, it notes that Sunflower Oil exhibits significant antifungal activity, particularly against *Aspergillus brasiliensis* ATCC 9642, among the oils tested. However, it's worth mentioning that all the oils displayed limited antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC-6538.

In summary, Table 1 provides a comprehensive analysis of the physicochemical properties of different oils, shedding light on their suitability for various applications and their potential use in food processing and industrial settings.

Conclusion

The growing demands in both industrial and nutritional sectors have prompted a search for oils derived from diverse seed varieties. In this context, seed oil was extracted, thoroughly analyzed, and its physicochemical properties were compared with those of sunflower, peanut, and mustard oils. The assessments encompassed parameters such as percentage yield, acid value, free fatty acid content, antibacterial activity, saponification value, agar diffusion test results, and moisture content.

The outcomes of this study reveal that peanut seed oil exhibits quality akin to that of other oils, demonstrating significant potential for both nutritional and industrial applications. Consequently, it is recommended that further research endeavors be pursued to harness the vast potential of this abundant and naturally nutritious oil source. Researchers have directed their attention towards peanuts as a viable alternative source of palm oil, poised to meet the escalating demand for healthy foods, skin oil, and the cosmetic industry's soap production.

Author Contributions: At first page.

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